

ICT IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The use of ICT in the Foreign Language Teaching and Learning is very important for providing opportunities for teachers and students to learn and operate in an information age. Education, particularly foreign language teaching has to adapt and renew itself to be compatible with the globalized society. This study aims to analyze the use of ICT in foreign language teaching and learning, which are the benefits, the main advantages of ICT and the challenges of ICT in foreign language. The recognition and implementation of ICT in teaching constitutes an integration challenges for our society.

ICT is the innovation which includes gathering, processing, storing and presenting information and also it involves collaboration and communication. The ICT can be used in different ways and spheres depending on purposes and aims. However, its role is rising and it takes great position in education system too. As Stephen reports the use of ICT reasserts the productivity of teaching and learning foreign languages.

The foreign language teacher is becoming more and more a kind of multimedia. He/she uses different technologies related to specific media as book (images, words / writing) images (iconic-flashcards), videocassette (video), DVD (images and sound, subtitles), Cassettes (voice), teaching files, games, simulations and interaction, and didactic games. ICT enabled the great opportunities for teaching and learning foreign languages and techniques experimenting with new engagement strategy by teachers and students for a more independent and interactive orientation towards learning. In teaching and learning of foreign languages educational software and the Internet are used more and more. Different typologies of software can facilitate the practice of linguistic skill through exercises, games and simulations. Multimedia software, except the fact that enables the delivery of foreign language in its authenticity opportunity also offers the best exercise of pronunciation and intonation.

However, disciples had been divided according to their future purposes and chosen sphere but there are still mixed leveled students can be noticed, as well as the levels and abilities of learners are mixed. Indeed, there will be problems which are having being noticed in multileveled classes for today. Naturally, they are connected with teaching and learning such groups. The two monthly pedagogical practice showed that the new generation, who are being taught at educational institutions, like academic lyceums or colleges and schools are more

interested in IT and ordinary teaching with only books or exercises are no more interesting and motivating them. Hence after observation, before starting the teaching practice had been chosen the mixed ability groups with some problems and prepared the materials according to the institution plans. During the practice, there was used ICT to overcome the problems which had been faced, like the effectiveness of learning, discipline, motivation and participation of students. For everyday teaching practice had been prepared additional handouts, topic based videos, songs, PPT presentations, except them the aspect course books also used. The influence of used materials was higher than it was expected. For instance: Videos and songs were used to make better listening skill. To point out, during a pedagogical practice, had been chosen the videos and songs connected with topics or grammar rules, despite the handouts and exercises there had been added the role play tasks or discussions, in the purpose of making learners to use target language and to strengthen some expressions, idioms, phrases or slangs.

PPT presentations. The presentations had been used to overcome with grammar problems and engagement of the disciples. The PPT presentations were grammar oriented and the effect of it was unbelievable, all learner's attention was only at presentation and grammar. There were multiple exercises which were based on the grammar rules.

On the basis of practice as a trainee teacher can suggest to those, who are starting practice to use presentations while explaining the topic or grammar rules, it would be perfect if the presentation will have practical exercises. However, while lessons were witness of issue that students like to guess and check themselves on everything.

Use video explanation tasks and brainstorming according to the video, since learners love watching and have unusual experience. Indeed, depending on the level of disciples, after the video explanation teacher has to explain the theme, one more time, but anyway learners will have a chance to face a real language by native speakers. Besides, videos can be used as an entertaining or interaction activity. Especially when it is fun searcher may notice how the learners will have interested in the lesson and how their motivation rises. They are also helpful to improve the students' critical thinking and pronunciation. Moreover, both are helpful to interest them into the subject. Likewise, it is better when the handouts and tasks are complemented them.

To sum up, taking all facts mentioned above can make conclusion that the use of ICT is one of the effective ways to awake the learners and making the teachers to move forward, but not backward and its influence on teaching and learning process is huge but that covers not only positive sights but also negative sights as well. Thereupon, in teaching every strategy and methods are effective but there should be the middle limit of them.

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